

gests no association between the two characters. The pooled estimate was also nonsignificant.

The absence of correlation between silvershoots and panicles and the significant correlation between silvershoots and tillering support the popular belief that silvershoots increase tillering, compensating for panicle loss. But it also may be argued that a hill containing a greater number of tillers is more susceptible to gall midge attack, because it provides more points. As such, more

tillers would be the cause of silvershoots.

Estimates of partial correlation coefficients between silvershoots and panicles after eliminating the effect of tiller differences were made. All estimates except one were negative, varying from -0.9751 to -0.0936 and significant in 5 cases. The only positive estimate was also small and nonsignificant. The pooled estimate of the partial correlation coefficient was -0.3156 , significant at the 0.05 level.

A partial regression analysis using the covariance model $y = f(\text{Tr}; X_1 X_2 X_3)$

where y stands for panicle, X_1 for silvershoot, and X_2 for tiller estimated the loss due to silvershoots for the pooled data. The result was $y = 1.84 - 0.3975 X_1 + 0.4584 X_2$. The estimate of R , the multiple correlation coefficient, was 0.7791, significant at the 0.01 level. Both partial regression coefficients were also significant at 0.01. The partial regression equation suggests that the expected net effect of a unit increase in the number of silvershoots is a drop of 0.4 in the number of panicles. ■

Resistance of modern rice varieties to the brown planthopper in Thailand

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Outbreaks of the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* have caused a rapid spread of ragged stunt disease in the central Thailand plain since 1973. But RD9, the first BPH-resistant variety released in 1975, has not been widely accepted because of its susceptibility to many diseases and its poor grain quality.

A greenhouse experiment was designed to determine the resistance mechanism in three varieties released in 1981 — RD21 (DML 105/Nang-Mol S-4/IR26), RD23 (RD7/IR32/RD1), and RD25 (DML 105/IR2061-214-2-3-3 // DML 105/IR26) — and in an RD7 mutant developed by gamma-irradiation which had shown BPH resistance. Experimental procedures were those used in the International Brown Planthopper Biotype Collaborative Project.

A free-choice feeding experiment showed no significant difference in the number of insects feeding on resistant and susceptible varieties. Antibiosis was indicated: BPH survival after 12 days was 6% on RD21, 7.5% on RD7 mutant, 14% on RD9, 20% on RD23, 20% on RD25, and 36% on RD1 (Fig. 1). The population buildup study also confirmed antibiosis reaction in RD21, RD23, RD25, and RD7 mutant. RD25

1. Survival of brown planthopper on modern rice varieties in Thailand.

2. Population buildup of brown planthopper (BPH) on different rice varieties 4 weeks after release of 3 pairs of adults, Thailand.

showed the highest resistance (no population increase) to BPH; RD1 produced 247 insects 4 weeks after release of 3 mated BPH pairs (Fig. 2).

Reaction of selected rice varieties to whorl maggot *Hydrellia* spp.

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During 1981 kharif, 22 varieties were grown in 20-hill rows. Two plantings were done, one at the usual time and the second 15 days later. Recommended management practices were followed.

The number of whorl maggot-damaged leaves was recorded on 10 hills/variety at 30 and 45 days after transplanting (see table). Ptb 12 and Ptb 21 had the least damage, Ptb 19 the most damage. ■

Incidence of whorl maggot damage on rice varieties at Aduthurai, India.

Variety	Whorl maggot incidence (%)
ARC6632	10.1
Banglei	8.5
Chemban	9.3
Chempan	11.6
Chitteri	10.7
Cheriya Chitteri	11.4
Kula Peruvela	11.4
L x H/2-281	12.4
Leaung 152	11.7
Nagrasal	12.9
Ptb 12	3.4
Ptb 19	16.5
Ptb 21	5.5
Ptb 33	13.0
Parakulam	10.5
Sulai	12.9
T 10	8.8
Vellai Langayan	11.4
Valsara Champara	14.3
Vellathil cheera	11.7
Lal Basumati	10.3
TN1 (susceptible check)	11.1